

ANALYSIS OF MARTIAN SOUTH POLAR STEEP SCARPS BASED ON CTX AND MOLA DATASETS.

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Introduction: Planum Australe (centred at the coordinates: -157.983°E ; 83.318°S) records the oldest sequence of glacial sediment accumulation on Mars [1-3]. It is a topographic dome composed by the South Polar Layered Deposits (SPLD) of late Amazonian age [4]. After the detection of anomalously isolated bright basal reflections [5] beneath the SPLD by the Mars Advanced Radar for Subsurface and Ionosphere Sounding (MARSIS) team, Planum Australe became a hot topic, due to the possible presence of liquid water at the base of the SPLD, in the area known as Ultimi Scopuli. Little is known about the basement underlying the bright basal reflections area. This is fundamental information, however, in the context of the current debates about the provenance and nature of the reflections.

Convex slope scarps have been observed on the surface of the SPLD. One theory to explain their formation and presence, is that they are caused by mechanical failure produced by outward ice sliding [6]. In this work, we present the preliminary results of the morphological and structural analysis of the South Polar Scarps (SPS) in Planum Australe to understand the mechanism and the processes for their formation and origin.

Data and methods: We used remotely sensed data acquired by the Context Camera (CTX) aboard Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter (MRO) that has a resolution of 5m/pixel, to produce a structural map at 1:6,000,000 output scale for mapping at scale no smaller than 1:10.000. We used the gridded Digital Elevation Model (DEM) from the Mission Experiment Gridded Data Records (MEGDRs) derived from Mars Orbiter Laser Altimeter (MOLA) aboard Mars Global Surveyor (MGS), bearing a resolution of 463m/pixel. The data were processed in full-featured professional Geographic Information System application ArcGIS 10.7.1 from Esri software packages. The basemaps were projected in Polar_Stereographic_Mars coordinate system.

We mapped the SPS by continuous solid line with triangular teeth pointing to the hanging wall, indicating the dip direction of the scarp. The maximum vertical throw is extracted by a topographic cross section across the slope break of the steeper side of the scarp center over MOLA topographic data. The azimuth dispersion of the SPSs is derived from polylines by polyline's length to determine the SPS orientations.

Results: Compared to scarps observed in other regions on Mars, the SPS in Planum Australe are characterized by different morphology. These linear structures exhibit asymmetric profiles from both lateral sides of the scarp. From one side they display convex slope with layered deposits, and on the other side a straight slope usually without any outcrops. The scarp face presents a relatively steeply sloping and the back scarp instead is gently sloping [Fig.1]. Several scarps are characterized by similar dimensions, striking, and steep slope. Some of the SPS appear to be deep depressions feature in ice deposits, while other are shallow with few meters of vertical throw. Many of these linear structures show evidences of mass wasting produced by structural failure [6] related to ice movement near the scarp slope streak and erosional features at the base of the scarp [Fig.1].

Figure 1. CTX mosaic image of the surface morphology related to mass wasting and erosion within the SPS. The black arrow indicates erosion by scarp retreat and mass wasting tails shapes. CTX product ID: CTX_V01_E-152_N-80; CTX_V01_E-156_N-80; CTX_V01_E-160_N-80. Central location: -153.401°E ; 76.822°S .

The azimuth distribution of the SPS in 30° bins rose diagrams show that these linear structures are oriented in the following strikes: ENE-WSW, EW and ESE-WNW [Fig.2]. The trends falls between $\pm 60^{\circ}$ and 120° to the north. The heterogeneous spatial distribution of the SPS between high and low-relief [Fig.2] seems to be related to disharmonic deformational style. This also include the horizontal distance and the scarp length. The steep scarps located near the south pole run through high-relief are extending for long distance compared to scarps in low-relief which are relatively short. The scarp segments ranging in low-relief are up to 274 km in length while in high-relief scarps reach up to 635 km. Current data show that the maximum vertical throw measurements for the SPS varies between high and low

relief. Large throughgoing SPS accumulate high vertical throw reach up to 1.6 Kilometer in high-relief compared to SPS in low-relief which exhibit tens of meters of maximum vertical throw. The scarp slopes in the studied area range from $\sim 5^\circ$ - 30° , while the dip slope ranges from $\sim 4^\circ$ - 16° . These measurements are close to the scarps reported by Guallini et al., 2012 [1]. A series of curving scarps observed at low-relief seem to have formed subsequently and have not been significantly modified by any flow processes, conserving a gentle slope.

Figure 2. Structural map for the mapped SPS in Planum Australe plain. View centered at -173°E , -84°N over CTX and MOLA data. The rose diagram (top right) shows the relative orientation of the SPS over polar stereographic map.

We mapped 282 scarps in length varying between 8 km and 635 km. Our preliminary results indicate that the maximum throw of the SPS falls within the range of previously reported measurements [7]. The log-log plot diagram for the cumulative frequency of SPS length show that the values scattering is best fitting a power law function, described by $N_{(>L)} = 68 \cdot 10^4 \cdot L^{-1.9}$ rather than the exponential functions defined by $N_{(>L)} = 400 \cdot e^{-0.012L}$ [Fig. 3]. Both functions display negative scaling relationship between the cumulative frequency and the length of the scarps. Based on detailed study for the Earth's faults by Soliva et al., 2008 [8], data belonging to the power law trend distribution on cumulative frequency versus length diagram, could be related to localized tectonic associated to scale invariant regime because the SPS appear in self-organized manner. The large SPS are potentially formed by linkage of smaller growing SPS and therefore enhances the development of the power law size distribution [9-10].

Interpretation: The difference in the maximum throw for the scarp face slopes and their trending consistently in high and low-relief could be the expression of either different driving process for their formation or different chronological events. Their asymmetric profiles and morphology suggest that the SPS in Planum Australe represent a surface collapses produced by ice-sheet sliding related to ice melting, as originally proposed in previous studies [4,6]. However, the disharmonic deformational style be-

tween high and low-relief and the spatial distribution of the scarps over Planum Australe introduces the possibility of compressive tectonic. We emphasize that the formation of the SPS is related to major compressive tectonic events alongside the ice-sheet sliding, responsible about the formation of polar steep scarps in Planum Australe.

Figure 3. Logarithmic plot of the cumulative frequency of scarps (N) vs. scarps trace length (L). Owing to the scarps length distributions, values are best fitting a power law.

Future Work: Here we present our first results based on structural and morphologic analysis of scarps in Planum Australe. We emphasize that the formation of the SPS is not restricted only to mass wasting related to ice movement [4,6]. We believe that Planum Australe is the subject of regional compressive tectonic events responsible for the formation of the south polar steep scarps. In future studies we will focus on the tectonic interpretations of the area, targeting specific MARSIS orbits and other datasets to establish a 3D and temporal picture evolution to understand the formation of the SPS observed in the south polar cap of Mars.

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